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Steady-state and Dynamic Models for Voltage control Evaluation in Normal Operation

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1. Introduction

1.1 The Transition to Renewable Energy and Active Urban Demand

The global transition toward a sustainable energy future is fundamentally reshaping the landscape of electrical power systems. At the distribution level, this transition is characterized by the ever-increasing integration of Distributed Energy Resources (DERs), such as photovoltaic (PV) systems, alongside the widespread electrification of the heating and transportation sectors through heat pumps and electric vehicles (EVs). While these technologies are essential for decarbonization, they introduce highly variable and dynamic power flows into local distribution grids.

In traditional power systems, energy flowed unidirectionally from central power plants to passive consumers. Today, households and urban communities are becoming active "prosumers" with dynamic power consumption and generation profiles. If unmanaged, the coincidence of peak solar generation and peak EV charging can cause severe grid bottlenecks, transformer overloading, and significant voltage fluctuations. Consequently, to maintain voltage stability during normal operations, there is a critical need to extract and manage energy flexibility from active urban demand, leveraging power-to-heat, power-to-mobility, and battery storage systems to support the local grid.

1.2 Voltage Control with Flexible Loads vs. Inverter-Based Resources

Integrating this diverse set of technologies requires recognizing that not all flexible assets interact with the grid in the same way. The challenges of voltage control fundamentally depend on the nature of the device:

1. Flexible Loads (Heat Pumps and EVs): Devices like heat pumps and basic EV chargers are primarily active power (P) loads. They lack the capability to control reactive power (Q). Consequently, any voltage control strategy relying on these devices must rely on modulating their active consumption to provide local voltage support.
2. Inverter-Based Resources (Batteries and PVs): Modern distributed generators and storage systems interface with the grid through power electronic converters. As the grid loses rotational inertia from traditional synchronous generators, there is an increasing interest in having these interfaces act as Grid-Forming (GFM) converters. Unlike passive loads, GFM converters actively establish the grid voltage and frequency, meaning they can control both active and reactive power.

This requirement introduces a major challenge for GFM converters. Standard control strategies assume the power grid is highly inductive (where the line reactance X is much greater than its resistance R). However, low-voltage distribution networks are typically highly resistive or mixed ($R \approx X$). In such non-inductive networks, a GFM converter's active and reactive power control loops become severely cross-coupled, leading to dynamic instability when standard methods are applied.

1.3 Scope of the Report

Because the physics and capabilities of flexible loads and GFM converters differ fundamentally, evaluating voltage control in modern distribution grids requires a dual approach. This report consists of two distinct but complementary approaches:

1. System-Level Voltage Control via Active Power Flexibility. The first part of this report, covered in Section 2, focuses on the system-level management of active demand. It specifically analyzes how heat pumps and EVs can provide grid voltage support. Energy flexibility is enabled by adjusting their active power (P) consumption in response to user preferences and nodal voltage status. This section demonstrates that a strictly P-only approach can maintain steady-state voltage stability for 24 hours.

2. Converter-Level Stability and Grid-Forming Control in Non-Inductive Networks. The second part, covered in Section 3, shifts the focus to the converter-level control, specifically for GFM converters. Because low-voltage distribution grids are highly resistive, concurrent control of P and Q leads to severe cross-coupling. This part investigates dynamic coupling and proposes implementing a Linear Rotational Transformation (LRT) within the GFM control loop to decouple the active and reactive power dynamics successfully. This decoupling strategy ensures that GFM converters remain stable while providing the advanced grid-forming capabilities required by the network.

Together, this combined analysis provides a complete evaluation of normal grid operation, demonstrating how to leverage P-only flexible loads at the system level, while overcoming the complex P-Q coupling challenges of GFM converters at the converter level.

2. System-Level Voltage Control via Active Power Flexibility

2.1 Introduction

2.1.1 Why flexibility¹?

The European Union aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 70% by 2030 and achieve climate neutrality by 2050. This transition will significantly increase the share of renewable energy sources (RES) such as wind and solar, leading toward nearly 100% renewable power systems. However, because renewable generation is inherently variable, the uncertainty on the supply side will also grow.

At the same time, fossil-fuel-based heating systems and vehicles are being replaced by electric heat pumps (HPs) and electric vehicles (EVs). The growing number of HPs and EVs adds pressure to the power system by creating new peak demands at the bulk level and causing technical challenges for local grids, such as voltage fluctuations, line congestion, and transformer overloading. For example, simultaneous charging of several EVs can overload upstream transformers or congest weak distribution lines, especially in dense urban areas.

To address these local and global challenges associated with high-RES penetration, energy flexibility offers a practical solution. According to the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE), energy flexibility is “*the ability of a power system to reliably and cost-effectively respond to variability and uncertainty in supply and demand across multiple timescales.*” In practice, this means that energy demand, whether for electricity, heating, or mobility, can be shifted, curtailed, or reduced in response to external signals. These signals may include dynamic electricity prices, time-of-use tariffs, incentive schemes, or flexibility requests from local distribution system operators (DSOs). By responding to such signals, flexible assets in the demand sector can unlock energy flexibility for the upstream network and benefit from demand response programs (DRPs).

2.1.2 Classification of energy flexibility²

- **Flexibility of Generation**

Generation-side flexibility refers to the ability of power plants to adjust their output in response to system needs. This includes technologies such as gas turbines, hydropower, flexible biomass plants, and grid-forming renewable units. Key capabilities include fast ramping, reducing minimum load, and efficient start/stop operations. These features help maintain system balance and provide reserves for reliability.

- **Flexibility of Demand**

Demand-side flexibility involves shifting, reducing, or modulating electricity consumption to match supply conditions. Common examples include controlled charging of EVs and operating heat pumps with thermal storage. Industrial and household demand response programs enable consumers to participate in flexibility markets. This approach reduces peak loads and supports the integration of variable RES.

- **Flexibility of Storage**

Energy storage provides flexibility by storing surplus energy and releasing it when needed. Technologies include batteries, pumped hydro, hydrogen systems, and thermal storages. Storage

¹ H. Golmohamadi. (2020). Agricultural Demand Response Aggregators in Electricity Markets: Structure, Challenges and Practical Solutions- a Tutorial for Energy Experts. Technology and Economics of Smart Grids and Sustainable Energy.

² H. Golmohamadi. (2024). Demand-Side Flexibility in Power Systems, Structure, Opportunities, and Objectives: A Review for Residential Sector. Energies.

enables time-shifting of energy and offers ancillary services such as frequency regulation and reserve provision, which are essential for maintaining grid stability under high renewable penetration.

2.1.3 Impacts of energy flexibility

- **Local Impacts of Flexibility (Distribution-Level and Community Scale)**

Energy flexibility provides several benefits at the local level, particularly for distribution grids and community energy systems. First, it supports grid congestion management by shifting demand or generation to prevent overloading lines and transformers. Flexible assets such as EVs, heat pumps, batteries, and PV inverters can also deliver voltage and frequency support, helping stabilize local conditions and provide fast response services. Furthermore, flexibility enables the integration of distributed energy resources (DERs), such as rooftop PV, community batteries, and heat pumps, without the need for costly grid reinforcements. This improves reliability, making neighborhoods and microgrids less dependent on central infrastructure. Finally, local flexibility creates economic benefits for consumers, as participation in demand response programs and local flexibility markets allows households and prosumers to earn incentives.

- **Global Impacts of Flexibility (Transmission-Level and System-Wide)**

At the system level, flexibility plays a critical role in balancing supply and demand across large-scale networks. It facilitates the integration of variable RES such as wind, solar, and hydro by providing balancing services. Flexibility also helps reduce curtailment of renewables by shifting consumption to periods of high renewable generation, minimizing wasted green energy. Additionally, it contributes to lower system costs by reducing reliance on expensive peaking plants and avoiding major transmission upgrades. Ultimately, system-wide flexibility is a cornerstone of the decarbonization pathway, enabling progress toward 100% renewable energy and net-zero emission targets.

Modern power systems must maintain a stable frequency to ensure reliable operation. Any imbalance between electricity generation and consumption causes frequency deviations, which can lead to equipment damage or even blackouts if not corrected quickly. To address this, system operators use frequency control reserves, which are categorized based on their speed and method of activation³:

- Frequency Containment Reserve (FCR) provides the fastest response to contain frequency deviations immediately.
 - ✓ **Purpose:** Stabilizes the grid frequency immediately after a disturbance (e.g., sudden imbalance between generation and demand).
 - ✓ **Activation:** Fully automatic and continuous; responds within seconds.
 - ✓ **Role:** Acts as the first service to keep frequency close to the nominal value 50/60 Hz .
 - ✓ **Duration:** Typically sustained for up to **15 minutes** until other reserves take over.
- Automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve (aFRR) restores the frequency to its nominal value after initial containment.
 - ✓ **Purpose:** Restores the system frequency back to its nominal value after FCR has contained the deviation.
 - ✓ **Activation:** Automatic but slower than FCR; usually activated by the TSO's control signal.
 - ✓ **Response Time:** Starts within a few minutes and can last longer (up to 30 minutes).
 - ✓ **Role:** Balances power flows between areas and supports system stability after initial containment.
- Manual Frequency Restoration Reserve (mFRR) offers slower, manually activated support for longer-term balancing.

³ S. Ghaemi, et al. (2025). Enhancing Power-to-Hydrogen Flexibility Through Optimal Bidding in Nordic Energy Activation Market with Wind Integration. Energies.

- ✓ **Purpose:** Provides additional balancing and replaces aFRR when needed for longer-term stability.
- ✓ **Activation:** Manual by the TSO (based on market bids or operational needs).
- ✓ **Response Time:** Typically activated within 15 minutes or more.
- ✓ **Role:** Used for sustained imbalances or to prepare for upcoming changes in generation/demand.

Figure 1 compares the response time and duration of different frequency services⁴.

Figure 1. Comparison of frequency services FRR, FCR, aFRR and mFRR⁵

2.1.4 Energy flexibility in residential sector⁶

Energy flexibility is studied across multiple sectors, including residential, commercial, agricultural, and industrial domains. It also spans different energy vectors such as electricity, heat, mobility, and hydrogen. Unlocking flexibility in each sector requires expert knowledge and tailored strategies.

In the residential sector, building clusters are the primary sources of flexibility. The key flexibility assets in buildings are EVs, HPs, batteries and PV panels (roof-top or on-balcony) which can provide significant flexibility to upstream grids. HPs operate using electric compressors and are typically controlled by heating operation controllers. These controllers can reduce or temporarily switch off power consumption in response to electricity price signals while maintaining indoor comfort. Advanced heat pumps allow modulation of compressor power without shutting down the entire system, further enhancing flexibility. Thermal storage, such as water tanks, can boost this potential by storing heat when electricity prices are low and using it later for space heating and domestic hot water during high-price periods. This approach assumes a strong correlation between electricity prices and RES availability, low prices often indicate excess renewable generation, while high prices signal scarcity.

EVs offer flexibility through coordinated charging and discharging cycles. Smart charging strategies can minimize electricity costs for EV owners by charging during low-price periods and, in the case of vehicle-to-grid (V2G) technology, discharging during high-price periods. However, EV chargers are a major contributor to transformer overloading, local peak demand, and voltage drops. To mitigate these issues, EV controllers can respond to signals from the local grid during voltage drops or congestion events by adjusting charging and discharging cycles. This coordination unlocks EV flexibility to support local voltage regulation and relieve congestion.

⁴ <https://energinet.dk/>

⁵ <https://energinet.dk/>

⁶ H. Golmohamadi. (2022). Demand-Side Flexibility in Power Systems: A Survey of Residential, Industrial, Commercial, and Agricultural Sectors. Sustainability.

PV systems paired with battery storage offer significant flexibility potential. These systems can store surplus solar generation during periods of high RES and low electricity prices, and later supply domestic demand during times of renewable scarcity and high prices. This capability enables peak shaving and valley filling, reducing stress on local grids and improving overall system efficiency. By aligning consumption with renewable generation, PV-battery systems contribute to both local grid stability and global decarbonization goals.

This report focuses on voltage control strategies for residential flexibility assets, specifically EVs HPs and combined PV-battery systems, to enhance their ability to provide local voltage support and improve grid stability.

2.2 Methodology⁷

In this project, a voltage controller is developed for residential flexibility assets, specifically HPs and EVs, to provide local voltage support. The controller is designed and tested through simulations using real-world data from the living lab demonstration site at Hyllegaard Høje in Denmark.

Hyllegaard Høje is a community energy site located in the Lejre Municipality, Denmark. The community consists today of 13 buildings (with each 3-5 households) in a cluster, but will in coming years be extended to include a total of 6 clusters). This site serves as a living lab for testing advanced energy flexibility solutions.

2.2.1 Demo-cases: Hyllegaard Høje

At Hyllegaard Høje, the Neogrid Community Energy Management System (CEMS) has been implemented across the cluster of 13 residential buildings, each consisting of 3–5 households. These buildings are connected through a shared low-temperature thermal network, known as a thermonet. Every building is equipped with a heat pump and integrated into a central digital platform. This platform forecasts energy consumption, optimizes operations based on electricity market prices, and responds to signals from the local DSO. Additional components include indoor climate sensors, solar PV panels, EV charging stations, and a battery energy storage system.

The Hyllegaard Høje development demonstrates a thermonet system as a promising heating solution for new residential communities. The site features a 30 km low-temperature loop of uninsulated ground-source piping that delivers ambient water to each building, where small heat pumps boost the temperature for space heating and domestic hot water. In dense residential areas, individual air-to-water heat pumps often create challenges due to noise and the visual impact of outdoor units, which conflict with high-quality architectural design. Ground-source heat pumps avoid these issues but are expensive, complex to install, and impractical on small plots because of thermal interference and coordination difficulties.

Thermonet addresses these challenges by centralizing the ground infrastructure as part of broader civil works. This eliminates noise and visual concerns while enabling efficient, community-level energy optimization through systems like CEMS. Although regulatory barriers currently limit its application in existing neighborhoods, the thermonet system at Hyllegaard Høje operates as a fully integrated energy solution. It combines local renewable energy, smart controls, and household-level heat pumps to deliver efficient, silent heating while enhancing energy resilience and autonomy for the entire community.

2.2.2 Network Model

To evaluate the impact of the voltage controller, a detailed network model is developed in DigSILENT PowerFactory. The model represents a micro-DSO network, including lines, cables, buses, and transformers, as well as flexibility assets such as EVs, HPs, PV systems, and batteries. These assets are modeled as active demands connected to the network, enabling realistic simulations of voltage control strategies. Figure 1 shows the network model developed in DigSILENT PowerFactory.

⁷ The technical methodology and majority of mathematical models are extracted from [SERENE](#).

Figure 1. Network model of energy community at Hyllegaard Høje, developed in DigSILENT PowerFactory ⁸

2.2.3 Intelligent Voltage Controller⁹

This section describes the structure of the voltage controller for residential flexibility assets, including EVs, HPs, PV systems, and battery energy storage systems (BESS). The controller design and mathematical models are presented individually for each asset type.

The voltage controller is implemented using a two-level control strategy to address forecasting errors and communication failures in scheduling device operations. This approach ensures that HPs, EVs, and BESS meet user requirements while supporting local grid stability. The bi-level control structure is explained as follows:

First Level: Handles signaling and re-coordination based on user inputs and preferences.

Second Level: Responds to signals from the local DSO and mitigates local grid issues.

At the first level, the controller estimates device operations by considering forecasted demand, electricity spot prices, user preferences, and the state of energy storage. Based on these inputs, it formulates an operating schedule. This schedule can be updated to compensate for forecasting errors. The first-level control requires regular online communication with the central control server via the internet.

The second level can override commands from the first level when necessary. It operates based on the upper and lower limits of energy storage and the voltage conditions at the point of coupling (POC) of controlled devices. Since state-of-charge and node voltage measurements are taken locally, this level does not require internet communication. As a result, it can correct scheduling errors while providing local voltage regulation where needed.

⁸ [SERENE](#).

⁹ R. Sinha, et al. (2024). Smart Operation Control of Power and Heat Demands in Active Distribution Grids Leveraging Energy Flexibility. *Energies*.

2.2.4 Voltage Controller for EVs

In this section, intelligent voltage controllers are developed for EVs to provide voltage regulation for the local grid, while meeting the EV owners’ preferences, e.g., SOC (State of Charge) and DOD (Depth of Discharge). In the EVs voltage controller, three control schemes are integrated to optimize the charging and discharging of the EVs as follows:

- Scheduled charging
- Up-/down-regulation
- Priority charging

Figure 3 illustrates the structure of the EV charging control system, which considers both the voltage at the POC and transformer loading. The figure shows how three control mechanisms correspond to different levels of flexibility, i.e., high, medium, and none, based on voltage magnitude and transformer conditions.

When the voltage at the POC is within the range of 0.98 to 1.00 p.u., the network has high flexibility. In this case, scheduled charging and priority charging are applied. It is important to note that demand flexibility remains valuable even when nodal voltage is normal because it helps maintain grid stability by adapting to real-time variations in electricity consumption.

As the voltage decreases to the range of 0.98 to 0.92 p.u., the network offers medium flexibility. Under these conditions, droop control combined with priority charging is implemented. Finally, when the voltage falls below 0.92 p.u., the network has no flexibility, and only priority charging is allowed to prevent further voltage deterioration.

Figure 3. EV charging control logic for unlocking flexibility based on voltage at POC and transformer loading¹⁰

To model the voltage controller, the following notations are considered:

- $SOC(t)$ is defined as the SOC of the EV battery at a given time t .
- EV availability is defined as the binary variable $X(t)$. $X(t)$ is equal to 1 if the EV is connected physically to the charger and takes 0 otherwise.
- $S(t)$ states the EV battery status, if the EV is connected to the charger and the battery is not fully charged, $S(t)$ takes the value of 1 and takes 0 otherwise.

Therefore, $S(t)$ can be formulated as follows:

¹⁰ R. Sinha, et al. (2024). Smart Operation Control of Power and Heat Demands in Active Distribution Grids Leveraging Energy Flexibility. Energies.

$$S(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } SOC(t) < 100\% \text{ and } X(t) = 1 \\ 0 & \text{if } SOC(t) = 100\% \text{ or } X(t) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The designated control mechanism ensures that the EV owners have the minimum preferred SOC level, SOC_{req} , at the time of departure. Therefore, the minimum required state of the EV battery, $S_{req}(t)$ is defined as follows:

$$S_{req}(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & SOC(t) < SOC_{req} \text{ and } X(t) = 1 \\ 0 & SOC(t) \geq SOC_{req} \text{ or } X(t) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

• Droop Control

Droop control is used to regulate voltage by leveraging the flexibility of EVs connected to buses in radial distribution networks.

To define the droop control mechanism, let $V_{POC}(t)$ represent the voltage at the EV's point of coupling, $I_{line}(t)$ the line current, and $P_{reg}(t)$ the regulation power provided by EVs. Since flexible loads respond differently to voltage and frequency variations, variable droop coefficients are applied to ensure optimal coordination among these demands when deviations occur in the power grid. The droop coefficients are calculated as follows:

$$k_v(t) = \begin{cases} \left(1 - \frac{V_{POC}(t) - 0.98}{0.98 - 0.92}\right) & \text{if: } P_{reg}(t) \leq 0 \\ \left(1 - \frac{V_{POC}(t) - 1}{1.1 - 1}\right) & \text{if: } P_{reg}(t) > 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$0 \leq k_v(t) \leq 1$$

$$k_l(t) = \left(1 + \frac{i_{crit} - I_{line}(t)}{1 - i_{crit}}\right) \quad (4)$$

$$0 \leq k_l(t) \leq 1$$

Since the node voltages $V_{POC}(t)$ along the radial feeder vary, the droop coefficient also changes accordingly. The lower limit for the voltage droop coefficient is set at 0.92 p.u. to ensure that no EV is charged unless under a priority condition discussed later, while keeping the terminal voltage above 0.9 p.u. with some margin for additional loads. The upper limit of 0.98 p.u. is chosen so that the load at the far end of the feeder can operate at its rated capacity at this voltage level. In Eq. (3), the voltage droop coefficient $k_v(t)$ is calculated based on $V_{POC}(t)$ to provide up- or down-regulation. Similarly, Eq. (4) defines the current droop coefficient $k_l(t)$, which manages line loading within the critical limit i_{crit} and the full loading of the connected bus. Finally, the overall droop control coefficient $k(t)$ is determined as the minimum value between $k_v(t)$ and $k_l(t)$, as expressed below:

$$k(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if: } C_{droop} = 0 \\ k_v(t) & \text{if: } C_{droop} = 1 \text{ and } k_v(t) \leq k_l(t) \\ k_l(t) & \text{if: } C_{droop} = 1 \text{ and } k_l(t) < k_v(t) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The parameter C_{droop} indicates the EV owner's preference to participate in droop control, taking the value 1 when participation is enabled and 0 otherwise.

• Scheduled Charging

In this control mechanism, EV owners can choose whether to participate in scheduled charging. To represent this preference, the binary variable C_{sch} is defined, taking the value 1 when participation is enabled and 0 otherwise. The scheduled power $P_{sch}(t)$ is generated either through cloud computing, using an optimal real-time solution for grid power regulation, or determined by an online or app-based optimization defined by the user and stored in the controller for offline use. If the user opts out of the scheduled charging program, the EV begins charging immediately at the charger's rated power P_{rated} . To distinguish between droop control and scheduled charging, two variables—flexible power $P_{flex}(t)$ and flexible control signal C_{flex} —are defined as follows:

$$C_{flex}(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if: } C_{sch} = 1 \\ 0 & \text{if: } C_{sch} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$$P_{flex}(t) = \begin{cases} k(t) \times P_{rated} \times S(t) & \text{if: } C_{flex}(t) = 0 \\ k(t) \times P_{sch}(t) \times S(t) & \text{if: } C_{flex}(t) = 1 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

The variable $P_{flex}(t)$ defines the flexible power required for EV charging, which can be based on the rated or scheduled charging power as well as the droop coefficient. $C_{flex}(t)$ represents the logical criterion used to select the appropriate charging power value for $P_{flex}(t)$.

• Up- and Down-Regulation

In power systems with high renewable penetration, fluctuations often lead to periods of excess or deficit in renewable generation. To counterbalance this intermittency, EVs can leverage their flexibility by charging or discharging to the grid, thereby providing up- or down-regulation in response to system imbalances.

To design the regulation scheme, let C_{reg} denote a binary variable indicating whether an EV participates in the power regulation program, and $P_{v2g}(t)$ represent the power exchanged between EVs and the grid. Participation requires the state of charge $SOC(t)$ to remain between 20% and 100%, ensuring the battery is never discharged below 20% during grid support. Define the control signals for up-regulation and down-regulation as $S_{up}(t)$ and $S_{dn}(t)$, respectively, along with the overall regulation signal $S_{reg}(t)$ and the regulation power $P_{reg}(t)$. Based on these definitions, the control conditions can be formulated as follows:

$$S_{up}(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & SOC(t) < 20\% \\ 1 & SOC(t) \geq 100\% \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$S_{dn}(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & SOC(t) = 100\% \\ 1 & SOC(t) < 100\% \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$S_{reg}(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if: } X(t) = 0 \text{ or } P_{reg}(t) = 0 \\ S_{up}(t) & \text{if: } X(t) = 1 \text{ and } P_{reg}(t) > 0 \\ S_{dn}(t) & \text{if: } X(t) = 1 \text{ and } P_{reg}(t) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The regulation power $P_{reg}(t)$ is calculated by the power system operator. To define the activation of the Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) signal, let $C_{v2g}(t)$ represent this control variable, which can be expressed as follows:

$$C_{v2g}(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if: } C_{reg} = 0 \text{ or } P_{reg}(t) = 0 \\ 1 & \text{if: } C_{reg} = 1 \text{ and } P_{reg}(t) \neq 0 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

$$P_{v2g}(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if: } C_{v2g}(t) = 0 \\ 0 & \text{if: } C_{v2g}(t) = 1 \text{ and } S_{reg}(t) = 0 \\ -P_{reg}(t) \times k(t) & \text{if: } C_{v2g}(t) = 1 \text{ and } S_{reg}(t) = 1 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Equation (11) defines the activation of power regulation $C_{v2g}(t)$ based on the user's preference C_{reg} and the regulation power requirement $P_{reg}(t)$. When the regulation signal is active, the power exchange $P_{v2g}(t)$ is initiated according to Equation (12). If the EV becomes fully charged during down-regulation or its state of charge drops to 20% during up-regulation, the signal $C_{v2g}(t)$ is triggered to stop further charging or discharging.

• Priority Charging

The EV control mechanism must align with the owner's preferences at the departure time. To guarantee the minimum state of charge (SOC) by that time, the controller generates a priority signal $C_{priority}(t)$. This signal is derived from the current SOC information $SOC(t)$ and the user-defined minimum required SOC_{req} at the estimated departure time. Based on these parameters, the formulations for the total time required to achieve the minimum SOC and the remaining time until departure can be expressed as follows:

$$t_{socmin} = \frac{[SOC_{req} - SOC(t)] \times C_{battery} \times 3600}{P_{rated} \times 100} \quad (13)$$

$$t_{remain} = t_{departure} - t + 900 \quad (14)$$

The controller logic activates the priority signal when the remaining charging time to reach the minimum SOC level is less than 15 minutes before the estimated departure. Once the priority signal is triggered, the EV charges at the rated power until the minimum SOC is achieved, after which droop control resumes until the vehicle is either fully charged or disconnected. During this period, the EV does not participate in grid regulation to ensure readiness for departure. The mathematical representation of this logic is given as follows:

$$C_{priority}(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if: } t_{remain} > t_{socmin} \text{ or } S(t) = 0 \\ 1 & \text{if: } t_{remain} \leq t_{socmin} \text{ and } S(t) = 1 \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

$$P_{priority}(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if: } C_{priority}(t) = 0 \\ P_{rated} & \text{if: } C_{priority}(t) = 1 \text{ and } SOC(t) < SOC_{req} \\ k(t) \times P_{rated} & \text{if: } C_{priority}(t) = 1 \text{ and } SOC_{req} \leq SOC(t) \leq 100\% \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

• Charging Power

Finally, the general charging power of the EV, $P_{char}(t)$, is computed based on its participation in the three control mechanisms: scheduled charging, up-/down-regulation, and priority charging. This relationship can be expressed as follows

$$P_{char}(t) = \begin{cases} P_{priority}(t) & \text{if: } C_{priority}(t) = 1 \\ P_{v2g}(t) & \text{if: } C_{priority}(t) = 0 \text{ and } C_{v2g}(t) = 1 \\ P_{flex}(t) & \text{if: } C_{priority}(t) = 0 \text{ and } C_{v2g}(t) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

This means that priority charging is enabled when the priority signal is active, regulation charging is enabled when the V2G signal is active, and scheduled charging is enabled only when both the priority and V2G signals are inactive

2.2.5 Controllers for Batteries and PVs

Electrical batteries provide bidirectional flexibility to the distribution grid: they can act as a load by charging from the grid or as a source by discharging to it. In this project, the batteries are integrated with PV arrays. When electricity prices are high, both the batteries and PV panels inject power into the grid. In this case, the PV-BESS system first meets local demand and then discharges any remaining capacity to the grid to maximize self-consumption. Conversely, during periods of low electricity prices or surplus renewable generation, the batteries are charged using PV output and, if needed, additional power drawn from the grid.

The Battery Management System (BMS) controls the charging and discharging schedule of the PV-BESS. Let $SOC^{BESS}(t)$ denote the battery's state of charge at time t , and SOC_{min}^{BESS} and SOC_{max}^{BESS} represent its minimum and maximum SOC limits, respectively. To prevent excessive cycling and avoid the hunting effect caused by frequent switching near these thresholds, a dead zone is applied: 10% above SOC_{min}^{BESS} and 20% below SOC_{max}^{BESS} . Consequently, discharging is suspended until $SOC^{BESS}(t)$ exceeds $SOC_{min}^{BESS} + 20\%$, while charging stops once the battery reaches SOC_{max}^{BESS} and resumes only when $SOC^{BESS}(t)$ falls below $SOC_{max}^{BESS} - 10\%$. Based on these conditions, the control logic for PV-BESS operation is formulated in the following subsections.

• Fully Charged Condition

When the battery's state of charge (SOC) reaches 100%, further charging is disabled until it discharges to a level equal to $(SOC_{max}^{BESS} - 10\%)$. This logic, referred to as Charging Condition $CC_1(t)$ or the Fully Charged Condition, can be expressed as follows:

$$CC_1(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & SOC^{BESS}(t) \geq SOC_{max}^{BESS} \\ CC_1(t-1) & SOC_{max}^{BESS} - 10\% \leq SOC^{BESS}(t) \leq SOC_{max}^{BESS} \\ 1 & SOC^{BESS}(t) < SOC_{max}^{BESS} - 10\% \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

• Peak Shaving Mode

Peak Shaving (PS) is a feature integrated into the BESS to reduce peak loads on the distribution grid during periods of high demand. When the PS mode is activated by the Battery Management System (BMS), i.e., $PS = 1$, charging of the BESS is disabled during designated peak hours (e.g., 17:00–20:00). This mode, referred to as Charging Condition $CC_2(t)$, can be formulated as follows

$$CC_2(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & PS = 0 \\ 1 & PS = 1 \text{ and } (t < 17 \text{ or } t > 20) \\ 0 & PS = 1 \text{ and } 17 \leq t \leq 20 \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

The overall charging condition of the battery, $CC(t)$, is satisfied when both charging conditions $CC_1(t)$ and $CC_2(t)$ are fulfilled:

$$CC(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & CC_1(t) = 1 \text{ AND } CC_2(t) = 1 \\ 0 & CC_1(t) = 0 \text{ OR } CC_2(t) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

• Fully Discharged Condition

The battery storage system is considered fully discharged when its state of charge (SOC) falls to 20% or below. This threshold is defined as SOC_{min}^{BESS} . The battery cannot discharge beyond this level. Furthermore, the discharge plan remains suspended until $SOC^{BESS}(t)$ exceeds $SOC_{min}^{BESS} + 20\%$ to prevent hunting, as previously mentioned. This control logic is referred to as Discharging Condition $DC_1(t)$ and can be formulated as follows:

$$DC_1(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & SOC^{BESS}(t) \leq SOC_{min}^{BESS} \\ DC_1(t-1) & SOC_{min}^{BESS} \leq SOC^{BESS}(t) \leq SOC_{min}^{BESS} + 20\% \\ 1 & SOC^{BESS}(t) > SOC_{min}^{BESS} + 20\% \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

• Power Export Mode

Power Export (PE) mode is a feature integrated into the BESS that enables selling power to the distribution grid. When the PE mode is activated by the Battery Management System (BMS), i.e., $PE = 1$, the battery discharges power to the grid. Conversely, when PE mode is disabled ($PE = 0$), the BMS restricts battery discharge and prevents power export.

In this mode, the BMS continuously monitors the power at the main meter and the solar generation $PV_{gen}(t)$. If the power exported to the grid $P_{export}^{BESS}(t)$ exceeds PV generation, the battery reduces its discharge to prioritize selling PV power during periods of high electricity prices or renewable generation deficits, while using battery storage to meet local residential demand.

The logical control for PE mode is formulated as follows

$$DC_2(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & PE = 1 \\ 1 & PE = 0 \text{ and } P_{export}^{BESS}(t) < PV_{gen}(t) \\ 0 & PE = 0 \text{ and } P_{export}^{BESS}(t) > PV_{gen}(t) \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

Note that the PE mode is represented as the discharging condition $DC_2(t)$.

• Charging and Discharging Power

Based on the aforementioned control logics, the charging and discharging power of the battery can now be expressed. The charging power of the battery is formulated as follows:

$$P_{char}^{BESS}(t) = [PB_{char}^{BESS}(t)] \times CC(t) \quad (23)$$

$$0 \leq P_{char}^{BESS}(t) \leq P_{max}^{Inverter}$$

In Equation (23), the charging power $P_{char}^{BESS}(t)$ is determined by the BMS and is constrained by the inverter's rated charging power $P_{max}^{Inverter}$, which supplies DC power to the battery via grid connection. Note that the variable $PB_{char}^{BESS}(t)$ represents the available battery power at time t , regardless of the charging condition. Similarly, the BMS determines the discharging power using the following formulation:

$$P_{dis}^{BESS}(t) = \begin{cases} PB_{dis}^{BESS}(t) & DC_1(t) = 1 \\ 0 & DC_1(t) = 0 \\ PB_{dis}^{BESS}(t) - [PV_{gen}(t)P_{grid}^{BESS}(t)] & DC_1(t) = 1 \text{ AND } DC_2(t) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

$$0 \leq P_{dis}^{BESS}(t) \leq P_{max}^{Inverter}$$

Here, $P_{dis}^{BESS}(t)$ denotes the battery discharging power, $PB_{dis}^{BESS}(t)$ represents the available battery discharging power, and $P_{grid}^{BESS}(t)$ indicates the power exchanged between the battery and the distribution grid.

2.2.6 Controller for Heat Pumps

The heat pump controller is designed to operate the heating system in a way that maintains indoor thermal comfort while also supporting the stability of the local distribution grid. The key idea is that heating demand is flexible in time, because heat can be produced earlier and stored without creating discomfort. This flexibility allows heat pumps to reduce their electrical consumption precisely when the grid experiences voltage drops.

The controller continuously monitors the node voltage at the POC. Under normal voltage levels, between 1.00 p.u. and 0.95 p.u., the heat pump follows its regular heating schedule. In this state, the device is free to turn on and off as needed based on household heating demand and the temperature of the thermal storage. However, when the local voltage drops below 0.95 p.u., the controller temporarily deactivates the heat pump to relieve stress on the grid. The heat pump remains off until either the voltage recovers (above approximately 0.98 p.u.) or the thermal storage approaches a critical low-energy condition. This ensures that residents' comfort is never compromised for the sake of grid support. In addition, if the household requests heating in "priority mode," the heat pump can continue operating regardless of voltage conditions.

This simple but effective control logic allows the heat pump to provide heat-to-power flexibility. During peak electrical demand—typically the period in which voltage is lowest—the heat pump avoids drawing power and instead relies on stored heat. When voltage is normal or high, it resumes operation and may even charge the thermal storage more aggressively. The resulting behavior reduces voltage drops, smooths the grid load profile, and still maintains the minimum heating requirements of the household.

The thermal storage unit, i.e., water tank, plays a crucial role in enabling flexibility from the heating system. Its controller works closely with the heat pump to determine when heat should be stored, held, or released. Heat storage is particularly suitable for flexibility services because it can absorb or release heat at nearly constant temperature, making it an efficient buffer for shifting demand away from critical grid periods.

In normal operation, the controller charges the storage when electricity is readily available—such as at night, during shoulder hours, or when excess solar PV is present. During these times, the heat pump can heat the storage to high temperature levels (often around 50–65 °C). As outdoor temperatures rise or occupants leave home, the heat demand is low, and the storage temperature gradually decreases, enabling long intervals without electricity consumption.

The control logic is simple: the system checks storage temperature, household heating demand, POC voltage, and user-defined comfort settings. If voltage deteriorates, the controller prioritizes supplying heat directly from storage rather than activating the heat pump. If the storage becomes low and heat is urgently needed, the controller will allow the heat pump to restart even under low-voltage conditions, ensuring thermal comfort is never sacrificed.

The heat pump-storage controller therefore acts as a regulator that shifts electrical heating load in time. By storing thermal energy during low-stress periods and discharging it during peak hours, it effectively unlocks power-to-heat flexibility.

The thermal power delivered by the HP is modelled as follows:

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{HP,heat}} = \text{COP} \cdot P_{\text{HP}} \quad (25)$$

where COP is the coefficient of performance and P_{HP} is the electrical power drawn by the HP compressor. The rate of heat delivered to the heating circuit is related to the heat-transfer fluid (HTF) flow rate and the temperature lift across the HP:

$$\dot{m}_s C_w (T_{\text{HP,out}} - T_{\text{HP,in}}) = \dot{Q}_{\text{HP,heat}} \quad (26)$$

with \dot{m}_s the Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF) mass-flow rate, C_w the specific heat capacity, and $T_{\text{HP,out}}, T_{\text{HP,in}}$ the outlet/inlet HTF temperatures. These equations quantify how much thermal energy the HP supplies when it is enabled, and therefore how long the system can rely on stored thermal energy while the compressor is disabled by the voltage logic.

2.3 Results

In this section, the simulation results of the case study in Hylegaard Høj are presented. As seen in Figure 1, the local power grid model is built up in PowerFactory DlgSILENT software. In this model, the local grid is connected to the bulk power system, shown as the External Grid. The power grid equipment is modeled, including transformers (two supplying transformers with numbers 41542 and 41543), power lines and cables (in a radial structure), household power loads (denoted with HHx, in which x refers to the house number), PV panels, heat pumps (denoted with HPx), and EV charging spots (denoted with EVx).

Voltage controllers are coded through DPL (DlgSILENT Programming Language) and integrated into the network elements, i.e., EVs, PVs and heat pumps. The control logic is based on the methodology, already explained in section 2.

Figure 4 shows the power demand of households for 24 hours. Based on the graph, the households have dynamic power consumption during the day and the peak power demand occurs in hours 18-22, when many residents get back home after working hours.

Figure 4. Power demand of households in the demo site

Figure 5 explains the transformer loading. Based on the network model, the local grid is supplied by two transformers. The loading profiles of the transformers indicate two peak periods in hours 10-15 for positive values and in 18-22 for negative values. The positive-negative values refer to bi-directional power, where positive values show the power direction from the local grid to the main grid and vice versa. Hereby, as the peak local demand occurs in hours 18-22, the peak transformer loading coincides perfectly with the same period. On the other hand, the positive peak value of the transformer loading occurs at midday hours when the local PV generation reaches the maximum value due to highest solar irradiation.

Figure 5. Loading percentages of the two supplying transformers

Figure 6 illustrates the daily profile of local PV generation. Although the generation capacities vary across different POCs, the PV generation follows a similar pattern. The generation patterns begin at sunrise, i.e., 6 am, reach the maximum generation point at 12:00-14:00, and gradually decline to near zero by sunset. As mentioned above, the midday peak PV generation is the main reason for the positive peak of the transformer loading.

Figure 6. PV generation in the local grid of the demo site for 24 hours

Figure 7 describes the daily profile of the EVs operation including active power and SOC. As can be seen, the EVs were connected during two periods: midnight 00:00-1:30 and evening 16:30-24:00. According to the SOC profile, all the connected EVs reach SOC of 80% at around 01:30

and no longer draw power from the grid until the morning departure, 06:00-07:00. Note that zero values of SOC indicate that the EVs are disconnected, meaning no SOC data is being monitored during those periods.

Figure 7. Active power and SOC of EVs for 24 hours

Figure 8 illustrates the operation of household heating systems, showing the power consumption of heat pump compressors, water temperature, and domestic hot water (DHW) usage. The graphs indicate that heat pumps consume the most power between hours 8 and 14. During this period, the average temperature of heat storage shows significant fluctuations. Similarly, DHW consumption is highest in these hours, reflecting increased household demand.

Figure 8. Operation of heat pumps and heat storage for the 24-hour study

Figure 9 illustrates the battery operation over a 24-hour period. The batteries are managed through a PV-battery control system, enabling them to store surplus PV power during high solar irradiation hours and supply local demand when solar generation is unavailable, particularly at night. The highest charging power occurs at midnight, when electricity prices are low due to reduced demand, and again around 10:00–11:00 during peak PV generation. Discharging takes place in three distinct periods: midnight (02:00–04:00), early morning (06:00–08:00) to meet rising demand, and evening (22:00–24:00) to support the increasing power demand from EVs.

Figure 9. Performance of the BESS for 24 hours operation

Figure 10 presents the daily voltage profile across different nodes of the local distribution grid. The permitted voltage variation is limited to 0.95–1.05 pu. As observed, all node voltages remain within these bounds throughout the day. The profile shows minimal variation during nighttime hours when loading is at its lowest. In contrast, greater fluctuations occur during the day, with a peak between 10:00 and 15:00 and an off-peak period from 18:00 to 24:00. The midday voltage rise is primarily due to high local PV generation, which slightly increases the average grid voltage. Conversely, the evening voltage drop is linked to high power demand, particularly from EV charging. Overall, these variations are very small, demonstrating that despite highly dynamic demand, local generation, and EV connections, the voltage controllers of EVs, heat pumps, and PV-battery systems effectively maintain voltage stability throughout the 24-hour operation, keeping the profile well within permitted limits.

Figure 10. Profile of bus voltages for 24 hours

3. Converter-Level Stability and Grid-Forming Control in Non-Inductive Networks

3.1 Introduction

The global transition toward sustainable energy systems is driving a paradigm shift from centralized synchronous generation to distributed, inverter-based resources (IBRs). As the penetration of renewable energy sources reaches 100%, power systems face new stability challenges. Traditional Grid-Following (GFL) converters, which rely on a stiff grid voltage for synchronization, are becoming insufficient for maintaining system stability in "weak" or islanded grids. Consequently, Grid-Forming (GFM) converters are emerging as a critical technology capable of independently establishing voltage magnitude and frequency, much like traditional synchronous generators¹¹.

The most common control strategy for GFM converters is Droop Control, which linearly relates active power to frequency (P-f) and reactive power to voltage magnitude (Q-E). This strategy is mathematically derived from the power flow equations of high-voltage transmission networks, which are predominantly inductive ($X \gg R$). In such networks, the control of active and reactive power is naturally decoupled. However, in low-voltage distribution networks and microgrids, the line impedance is often resistive ($R \gg X$) or mixed ($X \approx R$). In these non-inductive networks, the fundamental assumption of droop control is violated. The cross-coupling between active and reactive power control loops becomes significant, often leading to severe voltage oscillations and system instability.

3.2 Methodology

3.2.1 Power Flow in Networks with Different X/R Ratios

Consider a Voltage Source Converter (VSC) with voltage $E \angle \delta$ connected to a grid voltage $V \angle 0$ through an impedance $Z = R + jX = |Z| \angle \theta$ as shown in Figure 11. The complex power S injected into the grid is given by:

$$S = P + jQ = V \left(\frac{E - V}{Z} \right)^* \quad (27)$$

Expanding this equation using Euler's identity ($e^{j\theta} = \cos \theta + j \sin \theta$) yields the general power flow equations. Three cases of different X/R ratios will be considered.

¹¹ R. Rosso, X. Wang, M. Liserre, X. Lu and S. Engelken. (2021). Grid-Forming Converters: Control Approaches, Grid-Synchronization, and Future Trends—A Review. IEEE Open Journal of Industry Applications

Figure 11. VSC Connected to Grid via Network Impedance Under Three Distinct Operating Conditions: a) Highly inductive system ($X \gg R$), (b) Highly resistive system ($R \gg X$), (c) general ($R \approx X$).

a) Highly inductive system ($X \gg R$)

This case is the most common case in power system where system inductance X is much higher than system resistance R . In this case, R is neglected, and the power flow equations are simple. The equations for active (P) and reactive power (Q) at the output of the grid can be written as flow:

$$\begin{bmatrix} P \\ Q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{EV}{X} \sin(\delta) \\ \frac{EV}{X} \cos(\delta) - \frac{V^2}{X} \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

Finding the derivatives of P and Q with respect to E and δ that are converter voltage magnitude and angle respectively, and assuming small δ angle, such that $\sin(\delta) \approx \delta$, and $\cos(\delta) \approx 1$, yields:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \delta} & \frac{\partial P}{\partial E} \\ \frac{\partial Q}{\partial \delta} & \frac{\partial Q}{\partial E} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{EV}{X} \cos(\delta) & \frac{V}{X} \sin(\delta) \\ -\frac{EV}{X} \sin(\delta) & \frac{V}{X} \cos(\delta) \end{bmatrix} \approx \begin{bmatrix} \frac{EV}{X} & \frac{V}{X} \delta \\ -\frac{EV}{X} \delta & \frac{V}{X} \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

Because $\frac{\partial P}{\partial \delta} \gg \frac{\partial P}{\partial E}$ and $\frac{\partial Q}{\partial \delta} \gg \frac{\partial Q}{\partial E}$, it can conclude that for a highly inductive network, P is strongly coupled with δ and Q is strongly coupled with E , and this is the reason for designing P-f and Q-E droops control in transmission networks.

b) Highly resistive system ($R \gg X$)

This case is found in low voltage (LV) distribution level close to consumers. In this case, system resistance R is much higher than system inductance X . In this case, X is neglected, and the power flow equations are simple. The equations for active (P) and reactive power (Q) at the output of the grid can be written as flow:

$$\begin{bmatrix} P \\ Q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{EV}{R} \cos(\delta) - \frac{V^2}{R} \\ -\frac{EV}{R} \sin(\delta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

Finding the derivatives of P and Q with respect to E and δ that are converter voltage magnitude and angle respectively, and assuming small δ angle, such that $\sin(\delta) \approx \delta$, and $\cos(\delta) \approx 1$, yields:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \delta} & \frac{\partial P}{\partial E} \\ \frac{\partial Q}{\partial \delta} & \frac{\partial Q}{\partial E} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{EV}{R} \sin(\delta) & \frac{V}{R} \cos(\delta) \\ -\frac{EV}{R} \cos(\delta) & -\frac{V}{R} \sin(\delta) \end{bmatrix} \approx \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{EV}{R} \delta & \frac{V}{R} \\ -\frac{EV}{R} & -\frac{V}{R} \delta \end{bmatrix} \quad (31)$$

Because $\frac{\partial P}{\partial E} \gg \frac{\partial P}{\partial \delta}$ and $\frac{\partial Q}{\partial \delta} \gg \frac{\partial Q}{\partial E}$, it can conclude that for highly resistance network, P is strongly coupled with E and Q is strongly coupled with δ and for this reason, reversing droop control is required, designing P-E and Q-f droops control in LV distribution networks.

c) General case

In this case, system resistance R and inductance X are similar in value, so neither can be neglected. The equations for active (P) and reactive power (Q) at the output of the grid are:

$$\begin{bmatrix} P \\ Q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{EV}{R^2 + X^2} (R \cos \delta + X \sin \delta) - \frac{V^2 R}{R^2 + X^2} \\ \frac{EV}{R^2 + X^2} (X \cos \delta - R \sin \delta) - \frac{V^2 X}{R^2 + X^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (32)$$

Finding the derivatives of P and Q with respect to E and δ that are converter voltage magnitude and angle respectively, and assuming small δ angle, yields:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \delta} & \frac{\partial P}{\partial E} \\ \frac{\partial Q}{\partial \delta} & \frac{\partial Q}{\partial E} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{EV}{R^2 + X^2} (-R \sin \delta + X \cos \delta) & \frac{V}{R^2 + X^2} (R \cos \delta + X \sin \delta) \\ \frac{EV}{R^2 + X^2} (-X \sin \delta - R \cos \delta) & \frac{V}{R^2 + X^2} (X \cos \delta - R \sin \delta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

$$\approx \begin{bmatrix} \frac{EV}{R^2 + X^2} (-R \delta + X) & \frac{V}{R^2 + X^2} (R + X \delta) \\ \frac{EV}{R^2 + X^2} (-X \delta - R) & \frac{V}{R^2 + X^2} (X - R \delta) \end{bmatrix}$$

For this case, neither of the derivatives can be neglected, so this mixed impedance scenario represents the worst-case for control design. Any control action intended to change active power will simultaneously cause a significant disturbance in reactive power, and vice versa. Consequently, no simple SISO pairing configuration (diagonal or off-diagonal) can achieve decoupling.

3.2.2 Small-signal Dynamic Model

The power flow equations presented in the previous subsections represent the steady-state behaviour of the system. However, a dynamic model enables the analysis of the decoupling between the controller loops during transients. Including the output current dynamics, the small-signal dynamic power flow equations result as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \partial P(s) \\ \partial Q(s) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \delta}(s) & \frac{\partial P}{\partial E}(s) \\ \frac{\partial Q}{\partial \delta}(s) & \frac{\partial Q}{\partial E}(s) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \partial \delta \\ \partial E \end{bmatrix} \quad (34)$$

Where:

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial \delta}(s) = \frac{E V (\omega_n L \cos(\delta) - (L s + R) \sin(\delta))}{(R + L s)^2 + (\omega_n L)^2} \quad (35)$$

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial E}(s) = \frac{E (\omega_n L \sin(\delta) + (L s + R) \cos(\delta))}{(R + L s)^2 + (\omega_n L)^2} \quad (36)$$

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial \delta}(s) = -\frac{E V (\omega_n L \sin(\delta) + (L s + R) \cos(\delta))}{(R + L s)^2 + (\omega_n L)^2} \quad (37)$$

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial E}(s) = \frac{E (\omega_n L \cos(\delta) + (L s + R) \sin(\delta))}{(R + L s)^2 + (\omega_n L)^2} \quad (38)$$

Figure 12. Block diagram of the small-signal model showing G_{PQ} and $G_{QP}(s)$

Figure 12 shows a block diagram of the small-signal model, including the SISO controllers usually implemented for grid-forming converters, called the active and reactive power droops and denoted as G_1 and G_2 , respectively. Because of the coupling, a change ΔQ in the reactive power will cause a disturbance ΔP in the active power, which can be expressed as

$$G_{PQ}(s) = \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta Q} = \frac{-G_2(s)G_{12}(s)}{1 + G_1(s)G_{11}(s)} \quad (39)$$

The resulting disturbance in the active power will reintroduce a disturbance in the reactive power, both being related by

$$G_{QP}(s) = \frac{\Delta Q}{\Delta P} = \frac{-G_1(s)G_{21}(s)}{1 + G_2(s)G_{22}(s)} \quad (40)$$

Finally, this self-interaction caused by the coupling can be quantified by analyzing the transfer function

$$\begin{aligned} G_{coup}(s) &= G_{PQ}(s) G_{QP}(s) \\ &= \frac{G_1(s)G_2(s) G_{12}(s) G_{21}(s)}{(1 + G_1(s) G_{11}(s)) (1 + G_2(s) G_{22}(s))} \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

3.2.3 Linear Rotation Transformation for Power Decoupling

This subsection presents a Linear Rotation Transformation (LRT) to rotate active power P and reactive power Q such that P is coupled with the converter voltage angle (δ) and Q is coupled with the converter voltage magnitude (E).

The impedance angle $\theta' = \text{atan}\left(\frac{X}{R}\right)$ can be used to do the rotation, described by the rotation matrix:

$$LRT(\theta') = \begin{bmatrix} \sin(\theta') & -\cos(\theta') \\ \cos(\theta') & \sin(\theta') \end{bmatrix} \quad (42)$$

Then, the rotation is used to calculate a decoupled representation of the active and reactive power, given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} P' \\ Q' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sin(\theta') & -\cos(\theta') \\ \cos(\theta') & \sin(\theta') \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} P \\ Q \end{bmatrix} \quad (43)$$

3.2.4 The Relative Gain Array Method (RGA)

The relative gain array method determines if the coupling of a MIMO system, when SISO controllers are used on a certain input/output pairing (i.e., y_i and u_j). In particular, it is usually used to assess if the chosen pairing is right.

For a system with 2 inputs and 2 outputs of the form

$$\mathbf{Y}(s) = \mathbf{G}(s)\mathbf{U}(s) \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} Y_1(s) \\ Y_2(s) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} G_{11}(s) & G_{12}(s) \\ G_{21}(s) & G_{22}(s) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_1(s) \\ U_2(s) \end{bmatrix} \quad (44)$$

The RGA matrix Λ is defined as the element-by-element product of the gain matrix and the transpose of its inverse:

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda = G \times (G^T)^{-1} &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{G_{11}G_{22}}{G_{11}G_{22} - G_{12}G_{21}} & \frac{-G_{12}G_{21}}{G_{11}G_{22} - G_{12}G_{21}} \\ \frac{-G_{12}G_{21}}{G_{11}G_{22} - G_{12}G_{21}} & \frac{G_{11}G_{22}}{G_{11}G_{22} - G_{12}G_{21}} \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{11} & 1 - \lambda_{11} \\ 1 - \lambda_{11} & \lambda_{11} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

where (\times) is element-by element multiplication, also known as Hadamard product. For this particular case, the λ_{11} element is calculated as:

$$\lambda_{11} = \frac{G_{11} G_{22}}{G_{11}G_{22} - G_{12}G_{21}} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{G_{12}G_{21}}{G_{11}G_{22}}} \quad (46)$$

The results may be interpreted as:

- $\lambda_{ij} \approx 1$: the chosen pairing $y_j - u_i$ is a good candidate for an independent SISO loop.
- $\lambda_{ij} < 0$: The diagonal pairing will act as positive feedback and cause instability.
- $\lambda_{ij} > 0$: the pairing $y_j - u_i$ is probably not a good candidate.
- $\lambda_{ij} \gg 0$: control will be difficult.

3.3 Results

This section present simulation results to validate the coupling analysis for GFM converters connected to non-inductive grids, and to assess the performance of the proposed decoupling strategy. The results include RGA analysis of the system transfer functions with and without the LRT, small signal analysis of the coupling-related transfer function $G_{coup}(s)$, and time domain simulations showing the effect of applying LRT. These time-domain simulation were obtained using MATLAB® Simulink. Figure 13 and 14 shows the system under consideration and droop control considered for small signal analysis and time domain simulation.

Figure 13. Diagram of power circuit and droop control without LRT.

Figure 14. Diagram of power circuit and droop control with LRT.

3.3.1 RGA Results

As discussed in the previous sections, RGA enables the analysis of the coupling between SISO controllers applied to particular input-output pairings of a MIMO system. Figures 10 and 11 show RGA results for the system transfer function matrix derived in Section # for different X/R ratios, with and without LRT. In particular, Figure 15.a shows the inductive case, demonstrating the decoupling between P and Q as expected from the analysis and validating the choice of the $P-\delta$ and $Q-E$ pairings. Figure #.c shows similar results for the resistive case, confirming the suitability of the $P-E$ and $Q-\delta$ pairings. Finally, Figure 15.b shows the RGA result for the case with $X = R$, illustrating the strong coupling between P and Q, and that neither pairing is appropriate for independent SISO controller loops. Figure 16 shows equivalent results for the 3 different X/R ratio cases, after applying the LRT decoupling. The results show that $\lambda_{11} \approx 1$ for all cases which means that P and Q are decoupled and $P-\delta$ and $Q-E$ are good pairs.

a) X/R=10 (Inductive)

(b) X/R=1

(c) X/R=0.1 (Resistive)

Figure 15. RGA without LRT for 3 different X/R ratio cases.

a) $X/R=10$ (Inductive)

(b) $X/R=1$ (Mixed, Both)

(c) $X/R=0.1$ (Resistive)**Figure 16.** RGA with LRT for 3 different X/R ratio cases.

3.3.2 Small signal analysis results

Figure 17 presents the Bode magnitude plots of the Coupling Loop Gain, $|G_{\text{coup}}(j\omega)|$, which quantifies the interaction between the active and reactive power loops. In particular:

Figure 17.a shows the results without LRT. For high X/R ratios, the magnitude remains below 0 dB, indicating a stable system where cross-coupling disturbances naturally decay. However, as the grid becomes resistive ($X/R < 1$), the magnitude exceeds 0 dB at specific resonant frequencies. This positive gain regions indicate that the cross-coupling provides positive feedback with a gain greater than unity, leading to the exponential oscillation growth and system instability.

Figure 17.b shows the results with LRT. By applying the LRT, the system effectively mimics an inductive response. The plot on the right shows that the magnitude $|G_{\text{coup}}(j\omega)|$ remains below 0 dB for all tested X/R ratios, including the highly resistive cases ($X/R=0.1$). This confirms that the rotation matrix successfully suppresses the positive feedback loop, ensuring the system remains in a stable negative-feedback regime.

a) Without LRT

b) With LRT

Figure 17. Bode diagram of $G_{coup}(j\omega)$.

3.3.3 MATLAB® Simulink results (GFM Converter)

Figures 18 and 19 show the control circuits and the Simulink model, respectively, of the power system under study. An LCL filter is considered, and the converter operates in grid-forming mode. The short-circuit ratio (SCR) was set to 5 and the system was analyzed for two X/R ratios: 0.08 and 0.2. The Droop controllers and the LRT decoupler are shown in Figure 15. Table 1 presents the grid and converter parameters used in the simulation.

a) Droop Controllers

b) LRT

Figure 18. SIMULINK model for droop control and LRT block

Figure 19. Simulink model for power and control circuits

Table 1. Grid and Converter Parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Base power	S_{cn}	300×10^3	VA
Nominal converter voltage (L-L RMS)	U_{cn}	400	V
System frequency	f_n	50	Hz
Angular frequency	ω_n	$2\pi f_n$	rad/s
Base impedance	Z_b	U_{cn}^2/S_{cn}	Ω
Base capacitance	C_b	$1/(\omega_n Z_b)$	F
Converter coupling resistance	R_c	$0.005 Z_b$	Ω
Converter coupling inductance	L_c	$0.15 Z_b / \omega_n$	H
Transformer resistance	R_{tr}	$0.002 Z_b$	Ω
Transformer inductance	L_{tr}	$0.1 Z_b / \omega_n$	H
Filter capacitance	C_f	$0.05 c_b$	F
Resonance frequency	f_{res}	$10 f_n$	Hz
Damping resistance	R_{sd}	$1/(6\pi f_{res} C_f)$	Ω
Current control time constant	τ_c	1×10^{-3}	s
Current control proportional gain	K_{pc}	L_c / τ_c	-
Current control integral gain	K_{ic}	R_c / τ_c	-
Power Control Time Constant	τ_v	10×10^{-3}	s
AC voltage control damping ratio	ξ_{vac}	0.707	-
AC voltage control bandwidth	ω_{vac}	$2\pi / (10 \tau_c)$	rad/s
Frequency droop coefficient	$K_{droop,f}$	$0.2 / S_{cn}$	Hz/W
Voltage droop coefficient	$K_{droop,u}$	$5 / Q_{max}$	V/var

Figure 20 shows the time domain results for the system operating without the LRT, while Figure 21 presents similar results for the system with LRT. The test consists of three step changes in the active power, at times 5 s, 10 s, and 15 s.

Without LRT, the system is unstable. The results show that currents and voltages are tracking their references, but the active (P) and reactive (Q) powers continue oscillating around their

references without stabilizing. On the other hand, for the system with LRT, currents, voltages, and powers have a stable evolution and track their corresponding references.

Figure 20. Time response for many step changes in P without LRT ($X/R = 0.08$)

Figure 21. Time response for many step changes in P with LRT ($X/R = 0.08$)

Figures 22 and 23 show similar simulation results for the grid where $X/R = 0.2$. The results show that the system is stable without LRT, but the overshoots in P and f are higher than in the case with LRT. Using LRT improves the dynamic response in this case. The change in frequency for the case without LRT is $\Delta f = 0.15$ Hz, while for the case with LRT is $\Delta f = 0.06$, showing a reduction of more than 50%. It is also observed that the same percentage reduction occurs in the i_d current component and reactive power at the time of the disturbance.

Figure 22. Time response for many step changes in P without LRT ($X/R = 0.2$)

Figure 23. Time response for many step changes in P with LRT ($X/R = 0.2$)

4. Conclusions

This report presented a comprehensive evaluation of voltage control methodologies for modern active distribution networks during normal operation. As the grid transitions toward high penetrations of renewable energy and electrified urban demand, maintaining stable voltage profiles requires addressing challenges at both the system and converter levels.

Section 2 presented the performance of voltage controllers for active urban demand, including heat pumps, EVs, PVs, and electric batteries. The controllers operate in a bi-level mode: at the first level, they communicate with local residents to obtain user preferences, such as desired indoor temperature for heat pumps and preferred departure SOC for EVs. At the second level, they interact with the local grid to monitor nodal voltage status. This two-way communication enables the controllers to optimize the operation of active demands, unlocking flexibility in response to voltage variations at local nodes. Consequently, the controllers leverage power-to-heat, power-to-mobility, and storage flexibility for both electrical and thermal systems. Energy flexibility is extracted from demand, storage, and generation to maintain voltage stability. The controllers were tested on a local distribution grid in Hyllegaard Høje using a network model developed in PowerFactory DlgSILENT, with the controllers fully integrated. Simulation results demonstrate that, despite highly dynamic demand, the voltage controllers successfully unlock flexibility from controlled devices and maintain a stable voltage profile across the grid.

Section 3 revealed that relying on active power modulation introduces dynamic challenges when Grid-Forming (GFM) converters operate in low-voltage, non-inductive grids. Small-signal and Relative Gain Array (RGA) analyses confirmed that in mixed grids ($R \approx X$), active and reactive power control loops become deeply coupled. Under standard droop control schemes, commanding a GFM converter to inject or absorb active power for grid voltage support causes significant reactive power oscillations and may lead system instability. To overcome this undesired effect, a Linear Rotational Transformation (LRT) was implemented within the GFM control architecture. The simulation results from the RGA analyses and time-domain simulations validated that it effectively decoupled the active and reactive power dynamics.

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